

SYMPTOMS OF DISEASES OF CHILDREN 7-9 YEARS OLD WITH CEREBRAL PALSY AND THEIR CAUSES

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This article reviews the outcomes and causes of cerebral palsy in young children. The analysis of changes resulting from the disease is also considered.

Key words: cerebral palsy, mental retardation, psychological changes, hyperkinesis, epilepsy, neonatology, dysarthria, diagnosis, disease.

Cerebral palsy is a group of motor disorders caused by damage to the motor areas and motor pathways of the brain. The main feature in cerebral palsy is the presence of motor disorders from birth and their close connection with emotional disorders. Due to various degrees of motor disorders of the child, he is completely dependent on adults from birth. This negatively affects the child's emotional sphere, he lacks initiative and develops passivity in actions. A feature of mental development with cerebral palsy is not only its slow pace, but also its uneven nature, the acceleration of the development of some functions and the lag behind others. Violation of attention and memory is manifested in increased distraction, inability to concentrate for a long time, narrowness of its volume, predominance of verbal memory over visual and tactile memory. Distortion of space gnosis: it is manifested in the slow formation of concepts that determine the position of objects and parts of one's body in space, the inability to recognize and repeat geometric shapes, adding a whole from parts. Intellectual development of children with cerebral palsy may be preserved, but slightly reduced. According to E.S. Kalizhniuk, children with cerebral palsy can be divided into two groups depending on the level of mental retardation. (mental retardation and atypical oligophrenia). Children with cerebral palsy are characterized by the underdevelopment of the highest forms of mental activity - abstract thinking.

Typical manifestations of speech disorders in such children are various disorders of the vocal pronunciation side of speech. Therefore, the speech of these children is unclear and not very understandable to others. The severity of the violation of the voice pronunciation side of speech increases with breathing disorders: speech exhalation is shortened, the child breathes separately during speech, speech loses its smoothness and expressiveness. In the letter, errors appear in the graphic representation of letters, numbers, their specularly, asymmetry.

Almost all children with cerebral palsy are tired. With purposeful actions that require the participation of thought processes, they become lethargic faster than their healthy peers, it is difficult for them to concentrate on the task. If they cannot complete the task, they may refuse to complete it and lose interest in it altogether. Almost all children with cerebral palsy are tired. With purposeful actions that require the participation of thought processes, they become lethargic faster than their healthy peers, it is difficult for them to concentrate on the task. If they cannot complete the task, they may refuse to complete it and lose interest in it altogether. Personal development in children with cerebral palsy has its own characteristics. Emotional disturbances are manifested in the form of increased excitability, a tendency to mood swings, and the appearance of fear. Mood swings are often combined with inert emotional responses. So the child starts to cry or laugh, he can't stop. Increased emotional arousal is often combined with tearfulness, irritability, moodiness, discontent reactions, which increase in a new environment for the child and with fatigue.

An important developmental factor is also the child's perception of himself as part of a community engaged in useful work. Children are always interested in activities that bring great benefit to the community and practical benefits... This encourages them to engage in various types of socially useful work. Children with cerebral palsy are very sensitive to the attitude of others towards them and react to any changes in their behavior. Such children are very impressionable, they are easily offended, the reason for their displeasure or any negative reaction.

1. Corrective work should start as soon as possible, because due to the violation of some mental functions, other mental processes may be disturbed a second time. Corrective measures should be implemented through various games, because the leading activity at this age is play. The game helps the child's mental and speech development, acquire various skills and abilities.

2. It is important to combine children with different motor skills in classes, because it helps to develop and strive to improve their motor skills, they imitate more developed children.

3. It is important to organize the motor mode correctly during the children's stay in the preschool educational institution. During this period, it is necessary to choose the most comfortable position for the child: work at the table, games, sleep.

4. It is important to turn on the dynamic pauses uniformly in time during the correction exercise. (after 10 minutes).

5. The duration of corrective training, the complexity of tasks, and the increase in the amplitude of movements should occur gradually, taking into account the individual capabilities of the child.

6. It is important to activate during the session the functioning of all analyzers (motor, visual, auditory, kinesthetic)... Children should listen, watch, speak and use music, dances have a beneficial effect on the development of motor skills in such children.

Cerebral palsy is a polyetiological disease that often begins in the womb and continues to develop in the first years of life. The term "cerebral palsy" was proposed by Z. Freud (1893) to combine all forms of spastic paralysis of prenatal origin with similar clinical symptoms. A complex picture of neurological and mental diseases is observed in cerebral palsy, which is not only a slowing down of the speed of mental development, but also an uneven, unbalanced nature of the formation of individual mental functions. Cerebral palsy is a group of pathological syndromes that appear as a result of intrauterine, birth or postnatal brain damage and are manifested in the form of motor, speech and mental disorders. Movement disorders are observed in 100% of children, speech disorders in 75% and mental disorders in 50% of children. Movement disorders are manifested in the form of paresis, paralysis and violent movements. Disturbances of tone regulation, which can occur as spasticity, stiffness, hypotension, and dystonia, are particularly significant and complex. Disturbance of tone is closely related to the delay of pathological tonic reflexes and lack of chain formation of corrective reflexes. Based on these disorders, secondary changes (contractures and deformations) are formed in muscles, bones and joints. Speech disorders are characterized by lexical, grammatical and phonetic-phonemic disorders. Mental disorders are manifested in the form of mental retardation or mental retardation of all severity levels. In addition, there are often changes in vision, hearing, vegetative-vascular diseases, convulsive manifestations, etc. Many people do not know that only by understanding the child, by looking at the disease from the inside with the eyes of a little patient, you can really find a way out. After all, the developmental characteristics of children with cerebral palsy are a fairly generalized concept, and each child develops the disease independently, individually. Therefore, the approach should be chosen individually for each child.

Mental development of a child with cerebral palsy is characterized by impaired cognitive activity, emotional-volitional sphere and personality formation. Experts and parents working with these children have an important

task to prevent and correct these diseases. The specific tasks of this work for each child can be determined only after a comprehensive examination. Characteristics of personality and emotional-will formation in children with cerebral palsy may depend on two factors: biological characteristics related to the nature of the disease; social conditions - the influence of family and teachers on the child. In other words, the development and formation of the child's personality is significantly affected by his exceptional position, which is related to the restriction of movement and speech, on the one hand; on the other hand, the attitude of the family to the child's illness, the environment around him. Therefore, you should always remember that the personality characteristics of children with cerebral palsy are the result of a close interaction of these two factors. It should be noted that parents can mitigate the social influence factor if they wish.

Early onset of ontogenetic sequential exposure based on intact functions. In recent years, early diagnosis of cerebral palsy has been widely implemented. Despite the fact that in the first months of life it is possible to identify the pathology of pre-speech development and disorders of orientation-cognitive activity, correction-pedagogy, in particular, in speech therapy, work with children often begins after 3-4 years of age. years. In this case, the work is often aimed not at eliminating existing speech and mental defects, but at correcting them. Early detection of the pathology of pre-speech and early speech development and timely correction and pedagogical influence in infancy and early age can reduce and in some cases exclude psycho-speech disorders in children with cerebral palsy. The need for early correction and speech therapy in cerebral palsy is due to the characteristics of the child's brain - its plasticity and universal ability to compensate for impaired functions, as well as the optimal maturity of the speech functional system in the first place. three years of a child's life. Correctional work is built not taking into account age, but taking into account the stage of psychological development of the child. Organization of work within the framework of leading activities. Impaired mental and speech development in cerebral palsy is mainly associated with the absence or lack of children's activities. Therefore, the main type of activity for a certain age is encouraged during corrective-pedagogical activities. In infancy (up to 1 year), the leading activity is emotional communication with adults; at an early age (one to 3 years) - objective activity; preschool age (from 3 to 7 years old) - game activity; at school age - educational activity.

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